

THE ESSENCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF HERMENEUTIC COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: The article analyzes the content and essence of developing the hermeneutic competence of future music education teachers by forming the integration of music education and social and humanitarian sciences in music education, establishing interdisciplinary cooperation.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, hermeneutic competence.

At the current stage of development of education, the need to improve teaching methods, tools and forms of organization is increasing. Therefore, training specialists, in particular, creating educational-methodical and scientific literature suitable for the new era and applying them to the educational process, providing educational institutions with modern pedagogical communication tools, paying special attention to improving the quality of education necessary. In this regard, the development of a comprehensive and deep scientific-methodical foundation of modern music education in music education remains one of the serious issues. The development of hermeneutic competence is of particular importance for a professional musician.

In recent years, educational standards have focused not only on the process, but also on the results of education, on the formation of a self-satisfied specialist who is ready for professional activity, can adapt to society and benefit society. Competency issues A.V. Barannikov, E.A. Bystrova, V.A. Bolotov, V.P. Borisenkov, A. Dakhin, G.S. Zavatskaya, I.A. Zimnyaya, G.A. Larionova, O.E. Lebedev, A.F. Prisajnyaya, L.V. Savelyeva, G. Selevko, I.S. Sergeev, B.V. Serikov, M.A. Kholodnaya, A.V. . It was studied by such researchers as Khutorskoy, T.I. Shamova, N.M. Shansky.

The need to improve the hermeneutic competence of future music education teachers in higher education is determined by a number of social, economic, psychological and pedagogical factors. It should be noted that "the integration of musical art and pedagogy in the formation of the artistic and aesthetic competence of future music teachers, the whole set of components of the future pedagogical activity of the future music education teacher is still fully reflected not delivered. Because of this, the system of music teacher training in higher education includes a very complex number of components (musical

pedagogy, practical and theoretical, methodical, conductor, vocal-choir, instrumental education). At the same time, an integrated approach is necessary to study the special aspects of the preparation process of the future music education teacher for hermeneutic activity, which is a modern level of pedagogical science.

Currently, the field of music education is developing, including new forms such as distance education. In addition to online classes, these are telecommunication competition projects, national and international online science olympiads, quizzes and contests held using the Internet and electronic platforms, teaching methods of various subjects taught remotely. The telecommunication environment encourages students to try to form common cultural qualities, to make appropriate decisions, to analyze and sort the necessary information, having their own vision of the content of teaching science. Analyzing computer technologies, it is possible to indicate the following directions in which it is necessary to use them today:

- listen and analyze musical works;
- creating music; - simultaneously studying the theory and history of musical material in the form of text, audio-recording and video;
- creating personal music programs;
- obtaining various musical information using the Internet.

Through such opportunities, a future music teacher can choose his musical knowledge and position, and test his abilities in different types of music. The training of a future music education teacher with professional competencies is aimed at forming a person who can adapt to the socio-political, economic, information and communication space. In order to achieve better development of students' musical thinking and their musical abilities, "conceptual thinking skills" should be most prominent in the pedagogical activity of a music teacher. Based on the research related to music pedagogy, we came to the opinion that musical skill is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that allow one to competently perform one's musical activity. Russian scientist V. Asafiyev expressed his opinion in his works that "a music teacher in a general education school should not be an "expert" in only one field." said that he should be a performer who knows a musical instrument well. The professional competence of a music teacher is considered an integrated quality of a person, whose activity is described as a complex that combines various components aimed at improving professional culture and pedagogical skills. Therefore, it is necessary for the future music teacher to develop his professional skills, increase his musical thinking and

know musical performance well, and at the same time, his aesthetic taste and artistic creativity should be highly developed. Therefore, the future music education teacher must have several competencies: - the music teacher must be distinguished by his aesthetic taste and culture; - should be distinguished by high taste in musical activity;

- the teacher must have a very broad musical outlook;

- a music teacher should be a multilingual musicologist; - a music teacher must be a psychologist;

- should be able to organize the pedagogical process based on the requirements of the time;

- must have musical knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, it shows how important it is for the basic knowledge and skills of a future music teacher to include hermeneutic taste, skills and abilities. The task of developing hermeneutic competence in future music teachers is not only to teach understanding and appreciation of beauty, but also to encourage active participation in social life. "The problem of hermeneutic education has always been in the center of public attention. There has been a lot of talk about this lately. Some say that the main task of artistic and aesthetic education is to educate creative activity in students, others say that it is to teach to distinguish beauty from ugliness, and others say that it is the formation of high spirituality and developed hermeneutic taste. In fact, one of the main tasks of hermeneutic education is the education of hermeneutic taste. Aesthetic taste, which has its own place in the system of aesthetic consciousness, is one of the most delicate, conflicting, complex, interesting and topical issues. One of the unique features of aesthetic taste is manifested in the assessment given to reality, things or events as they are seen. A work of art that is seen for the first time, a book that has been read, is evaluated differently by the client depending on his age, profession, and level of education. This aspect alone shows that it is unique to an individual, but it is also important for society, that is, it is not a "personal matter". Expressed simply by the words "like it or not", it shows our aesthetic taste, worldview, and culture. Our views, experience, the society we live in, and the views of the era are also reflected in this assessment. Every student learns to enjoy beauty, feels it, and creates it when he communicates with ideologically and aesthetically mature works of art and art. On the contrary, a shallow scientific-pedagogical environment will make the taste of future teachers shallow. Although artistic taste and aesthetic taste differ from each other, they always complement each other. Artistic taste is based on aesthetic taste. Examples of fiction literature of

various genres - stories, short stories, classic works, their artistic images, pictorial means affect the emotions of future music teachers, help them to perceive and master artistic values, give hermeneutic pleasure. . Through this, their creative skills develop, and noble feelings begin to form in their emotions. As a result, their teaching efficiency and the quality of working with students will improve.

The formation of hermeneutic competence is not a one-time or even one-semester process, it should be continuous throughout the entire study at the university. Each new generation does not always create the basis of material and spiritual culture from scratch, but relies on existing cultural assets created by past generations. Historical succession is a necessary condition for the development of human society, including culture. Cultural assets are created at a certain stage of the society's development due to its needs and reflect the life of this society. There is no doubt that this legacy will serve as a means of ideological and emotional education that can provide significant mental and spiritual nourishment in shaping the spirituality of our youth, and will become a source of inspiration for all our artists.

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